

The Logic of Ritual Action in International Relations

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International politics abounds with rituals, but the rationale for ritual action has not been systematically expounded in international theory. This introduction to the special forum on *Ritual Action in World Politics* invites the scholars and students of International Relations (IR) to take ritual seriously. Flagging ritual action as an underappreciated, yet politically consequential genre of action in international relations, I make two main contributions. First, the paper conceptualizes ritual action in relation to the existing rational and constructivist theories of social action. I probe the rationality, functionality, and performativity of ritual(ized) conduct vis-à-vis the logics of consequences, appropriateness, practice/practicality, and habit in international relations. I argue that ritual action seeks to navigate uncertainty and mediate ambiguity in international relations by its promise to create enchantment effects. Second, the paper relates ritual to the already sedimented IR conceptual universe of practices, rules, norms, and performances, and provides a modular framework for the forum contributions to engage with. The forum's collective aim is to: (1) consolidate the conceptualization of international rituals, (2) deepen the evolving conversation on the features, forms and logic of ritual action in different empirical realms of world politics, and (3) outline a novel research agenda in the well-trodden subfields of deterrence, diplomacy and knowledge production in IR.

Existen numerosos rituales dentro de la política internacional. Sin embargo, la teoría internacional no ha expuesto, de manera sistemática, la razón de ser de estas acciones rituales. Esta introducción al foro especial en materia de Acción Ritual en la Política Mundial invita a los académicos y a los estudiantes de Relaciones Internacionales (RRII) a tomarse en serio la importancia de los rituales. Caracterizamos la acción ritual como un género de acción subestimado, pero políticamente importante, en el ámbito de las relaciones internacionales, lo que nos permite proporcionar dos contribuciones principales. En primer lugar, el artículo conceptualiza la acción ritual en relación con las teorías racionales y constructivistas existentes de la acción social. Investigamos la racionalidad, la funcionalidad y la performatividad de la conducta ritual(izada) frente a las lógicas de las consecuencias, la idoneidad, la práctica/practicidad y el hábito en el campo de las relaciones internacionales. Argumentamos que la acción ritual busca proporcionar una guía en la incertidumbre y mediar con respecto a la ambigüedad en las relaciones internacionales a través de su promesa de crear efectos de encantamiento. En segundo lugar, el artículo relaciona el ritual con el universo conceptual de las RRII, ya sedimentado, de prácticas, reglas, normas y representaciones, y proporciona un marco modular con el que pueden interactuar las contribuciones del foro. Los objetivos colectivos del foro son: (1) consolidar la conceptualización de los rituales internacionales, (2) profundizar en la conversación, aún en evolución, relativa a las características, formas y lógica de la acción ritual en diferentes ámbitos empíricos de la política mundial, y (3) delinear una nueva agenda de investigación en los subcampos ya conocidos de la disuasión, la diplomacia y la producción de conocimiento en las RRII.

La politique internationale regorge de rituels, mais les raisons qui expliquent ces actions rituelles n'ont pas fait l'objet d'une explication systématique en théorie internationale. Cette introduction au forum spécial sur l'action rituelle en politique mondiale invite les chercheurs et les étudiants en relations internationales (RI) à prendre le rituel au sérieux. Signalant le rite comme un genre d'action sous-estimé, mais important sur le plan politique, en relations internationales, je propose deux contributions principales. D'abord, l'article conceptualise l'action rituelle par rapport à la logique existante et les théories constructivistes de l'action sociale. Je sonde la rationalité, la fonctionnalité et la performativité de la conduite rituelle et ritualisée vis-à-vis de la logique des conséquences, du caractère approprié, de la pratique, de la faisabilité et de l'habitude en relations internationales. J'affirme que l'action rituelle cherche à gérer l'incertitude et à atténuer l'ambiguïté en relations internationales avec sa promesse de création d'effets enchanteurs. Ensuite, l'article établit un lien entre le rituel et l'univers conceptuel de pratiques, de règles, de normes et de représentations en RI déjà bien implanté, avant de proposer un cadre modulaire avec lequel les contributions du forum pourront interagir. Le but collectif du forum est de : (1) consolider la conceptualisation des rituels internationaux, (2) approfondir la conversation mouvante sur les caractéristiques, les formes et la logique de l'action rituelle dans différents domaines empiriques de la politique mondiale et (3) tracer les grandes lignes d'un nouveau programme de recherche dans les sous-champs bien établis de la dissuasion, de la diplomatie et de la production de connaissances en RI.

Introduction

International politics features many obvious rituals (Rappaport 1974), ranging from diplomatic handshakes and public apologies to carefully orchestrated state visits with their accompanying flag-raising and troop inspection ceremonies to military parades and international summits. In social theory from solidarist (Goffman 1959; Durkheim 2008 [1912]) to dramaturgical approaches (Turner 1982; Alexander 2011), ritual is typically understood to be a form

of ceremonial or sacred routine or spectacle that is invested with special significance and that, regardless of its reliance on repetitive performances, emphatically marks an activity outside the realm of ordinary contestation or variation. In the study of politics, rituals are generally conceptualized as specifically formalized social set-piece performances that are iterative, embodied, and meaningful, cherishing something held sacred, and foregrounding the symbolic in interaction (Saward 2017, 78). Whereas ritual broadly conceived is “a rule-governed activity of symbolic character which draws the attention of its participants to objects of thought and

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feeling. . . they hold to be of special significance” (Lukes 1975, 291), not all symbolic displays are rituals by default: what is or is not considered a ritual depends on both the particular pattern (or features or form) of that practice and its supposed social function. Rituals display and channel the power of symbols in world politics. If symbols are “orders to recall something from memory” (Langer 1957, x), rituals are reservoirs of embedded cultural conventions that derive their symbolic purchase from ordering time, distinguishing the permanent from the transient, the ordinary from the special, and thereby instilling meaning in human life (Han 2020; Xygalatas 2024). Rituals are generative of communities for their boundary-work around them and goods-distribution within (Farneth 2023).

The discipline of international relations (IR) has been showing increasing interest in the constitutive and facilitating role of ritual at various levels of world politics. Previous accounts have pointed at ritual repertoires in IR, outlining an analytical framework to capture rituals’ twofold logic of integration and fragmentation (Baele and Balzacq 2022); highlighted the role of ritual in sustaining relations of authority in historical and contemporary perspective, on the one hand (Kustermans 2019; Kustermans et al. 2022; Kustermans and Horemans 2022), and the disordering potential of world political rituals, on the other (Aalberts et al. 2020). Core international practices, such as securitization (Oren and Solomon 2015), peacebuilding (Schirch 2004), deterrence, and alliance politics (Mälksoo 2021, 2024, 2025), have been explored through the analytical lens of ritual(ization), alongside the exploration of concrete rituals in international security (Benford and Kurtz 1987; Gusterson 1996), international diplomacy (Neumann 2011; Lee 2013; Faizullaev 2013; Sending et al. 2015; Pacher 2018; Holmes and Wheeler 2019; Balzacq 2019; Wong 2021; Knotter 2021; Rösch 2021; Danielson and Hedling 2022; Davies 2022; Bramsen 2023), bureaucratic sociability (Nair 2020; Kuus 2023), IR knowledge production (Kurowska 2024), and the ceremonial aspect in the performance of politics (Elden 2021; Rai et al. 2021; Charoenvattananukul 2025). International legal scholars have adopted the concept of ritual/ritualism to examine the performing and materializing of international community and order (Chase 2005; Davies 2018; Aalberts and Stolk 2022), as well as human rights (Charlesworth 2010; Charlesworth and Larking 2015; Larking 2017), whereas a number of studies in the pedigree of David Kertzer’s (1988) concept of political ritual have applied the notion to a host of social institutions and phenomena (Lincoln 1989; Smith 1991, 2000; Etzioni 2000; Collins 2004; Celermajer 2009; Hutchinson 2009; Manners 2011; Zaiotti 2011; Kampf and Löwenheim 2012; Bentley 2015; Brentin 2016; Blake 2019; Solomon 2019; Kurowska and Reshetnikov 2021; Drieschova 2022; Ku and Mitzen 2022; Hom and Campbell 2022). But despite the burgeoning attention to various ritual practices in contemporary IR, the general parameters of ritual action in international politics remain yet to be pronounced. What amounts to ritual conduct in contemporary world politics? What drives ritual action and what is its purpose? What does ritual action enable in IR? What are we even looking for when looking at ritual action in world politics—symbols, magic, scripts, repetitions, conventionalization, staging/dramatization, specific time-spaces, choreographies, performativity, sacrality—or yet something else? How do all these elements hang together in the interaction ritual chains of IR (Collins 2004)?

This special forum is prompted by an observation that the understanding of symbolic action in world politics remains impoverished compared to the better attended logics of con-

sequences, appropriateness, practice, and habit (Linklater 2019). Rituals abound in world politics, but they have not made it on the IR’s radar of the logics of action for the prevalent ornamental understanding of rituals as “empty action,” effectively mimicking the “real thing” (Winzeler 2012, 112). Nevertheless, the broad agreement among sociologists and anthropologists that ritual has not gone anywhere regardless of the modernization process is steadily seeping into the field of IR as well (Gillespie 2008; Robbins and Sumiala 2016). The presence of ritualization in international diplomacy and international security politics compels us to examine what makes actors act ritualistically in world politics. This forum proceeds from the premise that for certain key realms of IR, “ritual is not simply an alternative way to express certain things, but that certain things can be expressed only in ritual” (Rappaport 1974, 5). Our collective venture probes the ontological and epistemological status of ritual in deterrence, diplomacy, and knowledge production in international politics with a threefold aim of (1) consolidating the conceptualization of international rituals, (2) deepening the evolving conversation on the features, forms, and logic of ritual action in manifold empirical realms of world politics, and (3) advancing a novel research agenda in the well-trodden subfields of deterrence, diplomacy, and knowledge production in IR. The contributions to this forum ask how rituals facilitate bonding, mitigate tensions, affectively charge, and fuel action in world politics.

In this introductory article, I proceed from the performative approaches to ritual, which suggest that rituals bring things about (rather than just bringing things to light) by the simple fact of their performance (Robbins 2016, 9). Accordingly, rituals do not only symbolize *x*, but actualize it (Alexander 2011, 38). Performing a ritual is a self-consciously constitutive action that not only communicates something but creates and enacts something as a social fact. Performative politics is theatrical, but this theatricality has productive power: rituals do things in the world, as well as to the ritual participants themselves (Saward 2015, 217). They create, sustain, and reproduce, but occasionally also disrupt institutional boundaries and actor identities. Meanwhile, there is hardly a single answer to the question of “how rituals work”: how and why rituals succeed cannot be explained by a general theory of ritual (Quack 2010, 183).

Since international politics is abundant with high stakes, high uncertainty, and limited control—key features deemed generative of rituals as coping mechanisms by anthropologists (Xygalatas 2024, 58, 81–2)—I suggest that ritual action primarily serves to navigate the radical uncertainty in IR. Whereas operational uncertainty consists of known unknowns and can be transformed into calculable risks by greater knowledge, radical uncertainty is characterized by unknown unknowns, which cannot be converted to risk (Katzenstein and Seybert 2018, chapter 2; Murray 2018; Katzenstein 2022, 3, 46). I conceptualize ritual action in IR as an endeavor of enchanting political interactions, the success of which is dependent on the *social magic of the performative*, such as in the case of credible deterrence (Bourdieu 1990, 1991; compare Landy and Saler 2009). Ritual action serves to charge salient interactions with the efficacious force of credibility and authority (Butler 1999, 115) by entailing a mixture of conventionalization, routinization, customization, or traditionalization, stipulation of rules for place and acceptable conduct, allusions to certain symbols and their sacral significance, and specifying the details of ritual performance (Bell 2009 [1997], 138–69). In IR, ritual is invoked to address situations where strategic and symbolic drivers of action seemingly intertwine and thereby seek to produce

distinctly charged political interactions and realities. Approaching world politics through the lens of ritual helps to make sense of the mesh of rationally calculated (strategic) and affectively charged (symbolic) interaction, further defying the long-contested rational/non-rational divide in IR theory (Kratochwil 1989, 47–56; Müller 2004; Chwe 2013).

I unfold this argument in three moves. The subsequent section engages critically the curious absence of ritual action in relation to conscious reasoning, normative appropriateness, implicit practical knowledge, and habit in the foci of IR theories of action. Ritual does not quite fit any one of the logics of action embraced in IR but straddles them. I will then sketch the parameters of ritual action in IR conceptually, relating ritual to the better-established IR conceptual universe of practices, rules, norms, and performances. The framing paper ends by way of situating the contributions to the special forum and reflecting on the broader implications of ritual action for the study of IR.

Logics of Action in International Politics

Theories of social action generally build on Max Weber (1978), who distinguished between (1) instrumentally rational action (*zweckrational*); (2) value-rational action (*wertrational*); (3) affectual or emotional action; and (4) traditional action (see Giddens 1979; Coleman 1986; Sewell 1987; Bourdieu 1998). IR's trope for engaging the question "what makes actors move in international politics?"—that is, *logic of action*, already betrays a rationalist bias in the reasoning of the disciplinary mainstream about how and why actors act the way they do. Accordingly, actors figure out ways of exercising their political agency in international politics by and large through a process of thinking and conscious rationalization.¹ Recent additions to the IR logics of action debate fundamentally question that premise, arguing for de-emphasizing the role of consciousness and rationality in theorizing agency, along with highlighting further layers of theorizing action in IR beyond the decision-making and political judgment of individual agents (Kornprobst 2011, 71). Theories of action in IR have honed the understanding of the rationale for collective social action and ways of mobilizing collective agency in world politics.

Addressing the question of why actors act the way they do, or what is otherwise known as "the fundamental problem of reason attribution" (O'Mahoney 2015), further requires a distinction between ontological and analytical logics of action. In other words, the question is not just about how intentions and motivations are supposedly related to decisions about how to act, but also about the modes of analytically accessing and making sense of the said ontological rationalities. Different logics of action in IR theory accordingly analytically privilege either discourse or practice, correspondingly zooming in on the narratives or embodied experiences.

The discipline has thus far addressed four major types of logic of action, focusing respectively on consequences, appropriateness, argumentation, and practice. The four oft-claimed mutually exclusive logics of action refer to the cost-and-benefit-driven rational action (or the logic of conse-

quences, embedded in instrumental rationality) (Keohane 1988; Kydd 2008),² constructivist rule abidance for the sake of identity consistency (or the logic of appropriateness, embedded in normative rationality) (March and Olsen 1989; Katzenstein 1996; Sending 2002), argumentative exchange to figure out a collective course of action (or the logic of truth-seeking/arguing, operating largely within the bounds of the logic of appropriateness) (Risse 2000), and practice-bound following of tacit common sense (or the logic of practicality) (Adler 2005; Pouliot 2008; McCourt 2016). The respective logics of action vary by their corresponding emphases on either individual or group behavior. Further contributions have highlighted the specific logics of habit (Hopf 2010; Hayes 2016), affect/emotions (Mercer 2005; Crawford 2014), and advanced a narrative theory of action wherein narrative reconstructs past occurrences and enables lived experience (Ringmar 1996, 66–92).

Yet, these logics of action do not come clear-cut in the reality of IR, as the reasoning of political actors "rarely ever follows a certain logic of action in a pure form" (Kornprobst 2011, 79). Flexing up about the alleged paradigmatic incommensurability of different logics of action is also evident in the scholarly practice of analysis, usually maintaining the rationalist-constructivist line of division in combining multiple action logics' threads, albeit not exclusively so.³ The springing of hybrid logics of action attests to the scholars' discontent about the empirical mismatch with the primary ideal types of action along the existing theoretical lines of division in IR.⁴ This is where ritual comes in.

But the trouble is that when people invoke "ritual," they are not necessarily talking about the same thing. As Ronald Grimes has evocatively put it, defining "ritual" is like trying to pin down "jazz" (2013, 186; see also Stephenson 2018b). There is no uniform definition of ritual in social theory and anthropology, with humanities and psychology further complicating the crowded conversation. Distinct conceptualizations with their discrete ontologies emphasize either expressive (Lukes 1975, 305; Bell 2009 [1997], 171), representative (DaMatta 1991), mediating (Debrix and Weber 2003), performative (Smith and Alexander 2005; Alexander 2011; Ringmar 2012; Robbins 2016), or normative functions of rituals (Kratochwil 1984; compare Smith 1987; Rai 2015). Incompatibilities consequently abound: for some, ritual refers to highly formalized activity with a nonutilitarian purpose (Buckser 1997, 410; Snoek 2006, 13; Winzeler 2012, 113), whereas others emphasize ritual's reference to "beliefs in mystical beings and powers" (Turner 1967, 19). Consider the following essential definitions of ritual:

... the performance of more or less invariant sequences of *formal acts and utterances not entirely encoded by the performers* (emphasis added) (Rappaport 1999, 24).

²The psychological variations of consequentialism admit the "bounded" nature of human rationality, highlighting various heuristics or mental shortcuts people use in decision-making (e.g., Simon 1957; Kahneman, Slovic, and Tversky 1982; Goldgeier and Tetlock 2008; compare Bruneau 2022).

³Consider, for example, Schimmelfennig's (2000) theory of rhetorical action where the choice mechanism is consequentialist, while the means to attain goals revolve around ideas (Kornprobst 2011, 76, fn 8). Bruneau (2022, 108) has made a compelling case for a theoretical convergence between bounded rationality and practice theory as an instance of rationalists' and constructivists' sharing of certain theoretical assumptions.

⁴For example, a "rational intuitionist logic of action" where automaticity (or acting on an autopilot) is located in belief-like psychological states (intuitions), providing individuals with pre-reflective knowledge, relevant for action (Holmes and Traven 2015).

¹In theoretical terms, rationality has broadly three understandings: substantive, procedural, and instrumental. Whereas substantive rationality involves judgments about value preference (such as life over death), procedural rationality deems a rational choice to be the product of an ends-means calculation before making a choice. Instrumental rationality refers to situations where an actor may have two alternatives and chooses the option that yields the most preferred outcome, utilizing assumptions concerning cost-benefit calculations related to threats, punishments, and pay-offs, often derived from game-theoretic models (Zagare and Kilgour 2000, 38–9).

...a mechanism of mutually focused emotion and attention *producing a momentarily shared reality*, which thereby generates solidarity and symbols of group membership (emphasis added) (Collins 2004, 7).

What transpires from these basic conceptualizations is that rituals call for delving into concrete interactions in specific situations, drawing our analytical attention to “place, setting, timing, and interaction, not only to abstract beliefs” (Smith and Alexander 2005, 26; Balzacq 2019, 120; see further Goffman 1959, 1969). Following Catherine Bell who has offered perhaps the most comprehensive catalogue of the concept of ritual across various fields and theoretical approaches to date (while remaining notably reticent to offer a compact definition of ritual of her own), a quest for a universal *ritual form* is indeed best to be abandoned for a context-specific study of concrete *ritual-like* practices in international relations (2009 [1997], 138–69). Bell’s take on ritualization as “a way of acting that distinguishes itself from other ways of acting in the very way it does what it does. . .for specific purposes” provides a basic clue for conceptualizing ritual action in international politics (Bell 2009 [1997], 81). Actions can become ritualized, for instance, by associating them with sacredly held values and/or traditions; singularizing them; attributing to them special power or influence; prescribing their specifics to fix their proper performance; situating them in special places and/or times; being performed by specially qualified persons; and inscribing them in a given community by repetition (see Grimes 2013, 194, for the family characteristics of ritual).

Bell’s emphasis on ritualization as a culturally strategic way of acting and exercising power naturally resonates with IR’s traditional foci on power and strategic manipulation (Bell 2009 [1992], 67, 179; see also Guzzini 1993, noting the potential of routine actions as rituals of power). Existing IR accounts generally seek an instrumental reason behind rituals and ritualization, observing their facilitating role in social coordination and provision of common knowledge (Reus-Smit 2017), social protest action (Chen Weiss 2013), and emulation/mimicking (Huang and Kang 2022), alongside rituals’ conflict substitution potential (see Desch 1996 for a critical discussion), and formative function (together with norms and scripts) to “constitute new fictions or reinforce old ones” (Steinberg 2002, 368; Brunsson 1989). Rituals in international politics can be instruments of collective claim-making, bearing on the rights and interests of others (Blake 2019, 5). Ritualization has been consequently understood as amounting to early institutionalization in international interactions (Vasquez and Mansbach 1983), but also to depoliticization (see also Edelman 1971). Barnett and Finnemore (1999) caution that “ritualized behavior” generated by rules and routines in international bureaucratic environments might leave their larger missions and social goals obscured. Ritual can be a politically handy tool, yet with potentially numbing effects. Being manipulatable and dramatizable, rituals do political work (such as generating a sense of community and solidarity) and hence can serve as a useful resource in conducting politics. The performative power of rituals incentivizes the ritual “entrepreneurs” of international politics to ritualize for a reason: aspiring to create (at least) a momentary community along with transposing people to another time-space through ritual action. But this is not the whole story.

Conceptualizing Ritual Action

Extrapolating from the distinct accounts of ritual in social theory and IR, ritual action in international politics emerges as embracing the co-existence of different logics of

action. Alike the logic of practice, ritual action sheds light on a common blind spot of individually rational *homo economicus* and norm-oriented, collective values-bound *homo sociologicus*—namely, “the implicit, tacit or unconscious layer of knowledge which enables a symbolic organization of reality” (Reckwitz 2002, 245). Ritual action is commonly associated with traditionalized conduct, or what Humphrey and Laidlaw (1994, 167, 98) refer to as the “archetypal action,” suggesting that ritual action is institutionally prescribed, already waiting for actors to enact it, not the expression of their personal motives or reasons.

My conceptualization of ritual action builds on practice theorists in IR who have most systematically sought to make sense of how the logic of practice (or practicality), *habitus* and tacitly shared knowledge drive social action (Pouliot 2008; compare Holmes and Traven 2015, 414). But I also depart from their work in important ways by zooming in on ritual action as a particular practice of social interaction straddling multiple action logics and generating its own specific way of knowing due to ritual being “simultaneously cognitive, emotional, and physical” (Grimes 2013, 323). If practices are a particular kind of action (Adler and Pouliot 2011, 5), rituals are a particular kind of practice. The interaction in and through rituals sets the profane apart from the sacralized elements of a society. Unlike the logic of practicality, ritual does not claim ontological priority to other modes of social action acknowledged in IR theory (compare Pouliot 2008, 276). While part of the family of practices, ritual has specific features and characteristics, being more emphatically rule-bound and reflexive compared to mere routines. Alike practices in general, rituals are competent performances—processes of doing something in the most general sense. If practice points out “the patterned structure of deeds in socially organized contexts” (Adler and Pouliot 2011, 5), so does ritual—but it does so in a specifically structured, normatively charged, and particularly enacted way, aimed at enhancing an emotional attachment, affective appeal, or dramaturgical effect of some sort. For example, the ritualization of deterrence interactions notably helps to cope with the reality of deterrence as a fragile phenomenon, constantly fighting the odds of the perceptions and intentions of the deterrer and the one intended to be deterred not necessarily aligning. The macro-practice of deterrence consists of a panoply of competent performances, exhibiting certain patterned regularities over time and space (Adler and Pouliot 2011, 6). These performances are ritual-like for their analog logic, reliance on certain sacral symbols (e.g., Article 5 for NATO, the presence of US forces for NATO’s eastern flank states; Mälksoo 2025), and collectively concentrated attention, emotion, and effort in the service of this strategic practice bestowed with special cultural and psychological significance.

For Humphrey and Laidlaw (1994, 64–71), it is by ritualization that “normal, everyday action is endowed with [a special] quality and becomes ritual. . .Ritualization begins with a particular modification of the normal intentionality of human action. Action which has undergone this modification is ritual action.” Everyday actions can be made special through stylization and formalization; by repetition and performing in a specific space; by linking actions to traditions and thus endowing them with symbolic meaning; by attaching special powers or consequences to actions; and by permitting only sanctioned individuals to perform certain actions (Stephenson 2018a). It is in this sense that ritualization emerges as “a way of acting that is designed and orchestrated to distinguish and privilege what is being done in comparison to other, usually more quotidian, activities” (Bell 2009 [1992], 74). In her compiling of “a ritual catalogue,”

Bell draws prominently on Bourdieu who contrasted ritual practice to other social practices for its special “logic of practice” (Bourdieu 1977, 109–13). Bourdieu highlighted that ritual strategy is not self-conscious knowledge of the rules of ritual, but rather a “cultivated disposition” or a “sense” which is embedded in the accultured body (Bourdieu 1977, 87–95, 118–20).⁵ Interpreting ritual action accordingly needs to start from unearthing ritual’s practical necessity—“the material (economic and social) conditions of the production of these practices and the collective understanding of the practical function they serve” (Bell 1990, 310).⁶ In order to begin to understand ritual as “action wrapped in a web of symbolism” (Kertzer 1988, 9), we need to further embrace symbols for they “are tangible and portable in ways that experience are not” (Marshall 2002, 370). Bourdieu’s account of social magic as an act “which consists in trying to bring into existence the thing named” (Bourdieu 1991, 223) is particularly productive for advancing the understanding of ritual action. IR studies drawing on Bourdieu’s political sociology thus provide a proto-theory for the conceptual effort to theorize ritual action in international politics (e.g., Williams 2007; Pouliot 2008, 2017; Adler-Nissen 2013).

The power of ritual action comes from the ability to generate social magic—“to produce collective recognition of the authority of the performative without which the performative cannot succeed” (Butler 1999, 128). The promise of generating enchantment effects sets ritual action apart from ordinary practices. Rituals are then a specific modality of social action for conveying and effecting social conventions as naturally given facts and communicating the constitutional ideas and rules at the international systemic level (Bell 2009 [1997], 128–35; Bucher and Eckl 2022, 323). While frequently put into strategic use in IR, ritual is less a strategy of action per se than a behavioral genre or action repertoire exercised in international politics for various performative effects (see also Swidler 1986). Underpinning the non-contractual basis of various social exchanges, ritual comes before and runs deeper than purely strategic action.

Ritual action can serve multiple functions in international politics from consolidating a community and producing solidarity to cementing or transforming a status quo; legitimizing change; confirming or subverting an international hierarchy; and buttressing or enhancing a particular social positioning. In religion and politics alike, ritual appears as a mediating mechanism of fundamental dilemmas in (political) life, not an impetus of action in the first place.⁷ Rituals help to navigate difficult decisions and negotiate ambiguity. As “symbolic techniques of making oneself home in the world,” rituals render time habitable and accessible, stabilizing life (Han 2020, 2). Individually and collectively, rituals further feature as coping mechanisms with critical situations, thus serving evident ontological security functions for ritual participants (Giesen 2006, 338). Ritual action can hence be rationally purposeful, but it is always generative of effects that cannot be rationally entirely planned or controlled for. The stewardship of the sacred through ritual is particularly advantageous for identity reproduction in uncertain times as ritual provides

actors with an ingrained background practice to reach for in order to hold the social together in times of trouble. Yet, while rituals can be strategically dramatized to boost community and authority and enhance one’s communicative credibility, they can also backfire and have disruptive effects instead of the intended ones. Whereas the standard focus of ritual scholarship concerns social solidarity and preserving existing orders (Goffman 1959; Durkheim 2008 [1912]), performativity of rituals demonstrates their re-ordering and dis-ordering effects, where they can stabilize as well as destabilize subjectivities and communities (Lukes 1975; Pfaff and Yang 2001) or provide leeway for resistance and new forms of political becoming (Aalberts et al. 2020).

Embodied ritual enactments crystallize certain values, meanings, and beliefs; they play on, and amplify particular social connections. As Goffman (1964, 136) observed, the regulations of face-to-face interactions have a structure that is “not intrinsically linguistic in character, however expressed through a linguistic medium.” Alertness to ritual conduct in international politics therefore tunes a researcher in on the “nonwritable” behaviors—gestures, postures, tones of voice, rhythm, and movement besides the ritualized verbal communication. Alike the logic of practicality, ritual conduct is complementary to the recognized logics of social action in IR. It channels and facilitates the generation of the background knowledge and the parameters of the possible, informing conscious action. But ritual action at the level of political collectives also enables to perform subversive registers of action, otherwise downplayed or denied in the other channels of communication. The ability of collective rituals to bring people temporarily into another state (Collins 2004, 7; Seligman and Weller 2012, 201) affects ritual participants for its potential to create the “enchantment effect” (Bennett 2001). Ritual action works tacitly, rather than directly, as “much that ritual accomplishes takes place behind the scenes, at the level of the cognitive and the emotional” (Boddy 2010, 113).

Both in its registers and normative substance, ritual action has further overlay with the constructivist logic of appropriateness, highlighting the systemic repercussions of ritualization in international interactions. In IR, ritual action is frequently invoked to consolidate or manage an order of a particular international activity, for instance, via public ceremonies and staged speech acts evoking and animating relevant symbols. Following Goffman (1983, 5), the orderliness of the interaction order “is predicated on a large base of shared cognitive presuppositions, if not normative ones, and self-sustained restraint.” Any interaction order—including the ones of diplomacy, deterrence, and IR knowledge-making—draws on systems of enabling and restraining conventions, the ground rules of a game of sorts. Goffman (1967, 53) distinguishes between substantive (or “intrinsic,” alternatively, “instrumental”) and ceremonial (or “expressive,” also “ritual”) rules, with the former guiding conduct in regard to matters that are felt to have significance in their own right, whereas the latter set the boundaries for appropriate action in matters of supposedly secondary or no significance in their own right. An example of a substantive rule in the modern interaction order of international security is the prohibition against the use of force in IR (except for self-defense) and the states’ expected abidance by the international humanitarian law, regulating the conduct in armed conflict. Meanwhile, negotiations of generally agreed conventions (or “enacted models for how things ought to be”) (Grimes 2013, 331) at the level of conversational encounters, formal meetings, stage performances, and celebratory social occasions feature as *anti-rituals* (Goffman 1967, 86; Raab 2019, 52). These

⁵Compare Bourdieu’s notion of habitus referring to “systems of durable, transposable dispositions” that make up people’s shared and unspoken know-how and practices (Bell 1990; Bourdieu 1990). Adler and Pouliot (2011, 17) subsume rituals together with expectations, dispositions, skills, and techniques under the category of “background knowledge” that provides the basis for the constitution of practices.

⁶Compare Marshall (2002, 376) arguing that “[r]itual behavior is most when it has no utilitarian purpose.”

⁷Compare with the logic of arguing, also presented as a response to particular circumstances.

“ceremonial profanations” or ritual transgressions might occur inadvertently or in a calculated manner, constituting symbolic actions that could be interpreted as utter contempt for the interaction partners.⁸ Ceremonial profanations (or “spite actions”) might also exist vis-à-vis substantive rules, abusing substantive order for ceremonial purposes (Raab 2019, 86). As Schelling (1966, 52) maintains, the appearance of “breach in the rules” can be accentuated to “shock the other side, creating a sense of danger, signaling initiative, determination, or even recklessness, and so to intimidate the other and to give it pause.” As a flip side of ritual conduct in a particular interaction order, explicit anti-rituals threaten to unsettle the ingrained “ritual rules” of interaction. Consider, for instance, how the Russian leadership has openly challenged the ritual rules of respectful international conduct by normalizing diplomatic insults in various stage performances of the Russian state in the build-up and during the full-scale invasion of Ukraine, thus demonstrating active condescension toward its interaction partners (Aron 2022). Ritual transgressions are prone to generate symbolic counter-responses in kind, such as a walk-out of 140+ diplomats from the UN Human Rights Council in response to Russian Foreign Minister Sergey Lavrov’s speech of March 1, 2022, justifying the aggression against Ukraine.

While ritual is a highly polysemic notion, its ontology rests upon a solid element of intersubjectivity, not unlike that of international regimes (Kratowil and Ruggie 1986, 764). Ritual action emerges as a particular combination of multiple action logics for certain circumstances. Understanding the “logic” of ritual action therefore requires grasping the political logic of *ritualizing* a particular political activity and interaction, rather than grappling with a logic of logic (Bourdieu 1977, 109, 221 fn 25). I use the term “ritual” in the context of international interactions to refer to demarcated, recurring, and occasionally dramatized acts that follow a stipulated convention of “this is how it should work” (*the logic of practicality*), a normative script of the appropriate limits and legitimate uses of the said practice (*the logic of appropriateness*), and a rationale for exploiting the practice in question, or mobilizing particular elements of it to a certain performative aspiration, goal, or effect (*the logic of consequences*). To illustrate via a negative example of a deliberately mis-performed ritual: when a newly elected US President Trump failed to reaffirm the US commitment to NATO’s mutual defense pledge at his first summit with the allies in Brussels in 2017, his conduct rubbed against the ingrained expectations about the performative reiteration of Article 5 as “the most sacred symbol” of NATO and as such, the necessary glue of the solidary North Atlantic community. Trump’s defiance of the expected bounds of action undermined the “we-feeling” between NATO members, which, upon the due ritual performance of the US commitment, would presumably have emerged reassured (Koschut 2024). Trump’s conduct not only disrupted the sacred core of the North Atlantic Alliance but purposefully sought to reduce and subjugate the understanding of the ritual exclusively to the instrumentalist logic. By his intentional refusal to play along with the expected pattern of ritual reaffirmation of the allies, the US president manipulated the traditional grammar and choreography of such meetings to transactionalist ends to press the allies to take the US concerns about the intra-alliance burden-sharing seriously.⁹

Like symbolic politics more generally, ritual action “does not constitute a full alternative model of collective action, but

rather an explanation for an important dynamic that operates at varying levels during particular episodes of collective action,” blending symbolic and structural elements (Brysk 1995, 561). Instead, ritual action bridges and combines various categories and logics of action, bringing together the symbolic, reflexive, and reflective; featuring routines, habitual, mundane (Goffman 1967), and ceremonial (Rai 2015, 159); generating affective energy communality, albeit potentially also disruption. By drawing boundaries around communities, distributing goods, and prefiguring alternative ways of living together rituals unsettle a sharp distinction between expressive and effective action (Farneth 2023, 13).

Since ritual bridges individual and social (Bellah 2005, 194), ritual action is emphatically relational: it conceives of agency as not an individual property but as something pertaining to “evolutionary social processes made up by interdependent actors through their trans-actions” (Dépelteau 2008, 62). As a particular kind of social practice, ritual can become habitual over time, but political rituals are generally not mindless, but deliberate and intentional. Unlike habits, rituals are conscious and effortful acts. Ritual combines the affective and embodied, thus intertwining reasoning and sensing on the actors’ part. Ritual behavior is a reminder that “[m]ost of the time we don’t explain to either ourselves or others what we do, because we don’t have the time as we get on with our life” (Bloch 2016, 88). Ritual combines purpose-oriented and affectively geared action, where improvisation and play have an important role besides cognitively pre-planned conduct (compare Cornut 2018). The study of ritual action consequently advances the understanding of the sub-cognitive and affectively charged basis of (inter)action. Ritual further serves as a mirror into how things are desired to be (or considered *ought to be*).¹⁰

Ritualization refers to the intentional use of certain practices, ritual action by design. But the deliberate entering into a political ritual cannot be fully “proofed” against the unexpected and uncontrollable effects of ritual action. Nor does the functional utility of rituals exhaust their meaningfulness as a fundamental element of international social life. While intentionally designed to cope with uncertainty, collective political rituals frequently mobilize constructive ambiguity for their participants and audiences, leaving room for interpretation about their rationale. The ambiguity is the most notable political asset of ritual conduct, but also its main contingency (Goffman 1983, 4; Seligman and Weller 2012, 25). Regardless of any deliberate orchestration of ritual action, ritual is “not entirely encoded by the performer” (Rappaport 1999, 24). Hence, whereas ritual action in IR generally has a declared aim (*rationality*) and functions (ascribed to it as a *post hoc* rationalization, i.e., *functionality*), the constitutive effects of ritual do not necessarily align with the original intentions behind the ritual. As Molly Farneth (2023, 19) maintains, “What makes an enactment of a ritual successful is not always fully spelled out beforehand. . . the conditions for success are often recognized and negotiated after the fact.”¹¹ What ritual conduct does (*performativity*) can be analytically distinguished from its intentional effects. For example, navigating radical uncertainty and the attempted building of social cohesion for a particular social self can inadvertently signal a bid for a rigid boundary between the said community and the others (Table 1). When a multinational group of NATO soldiers sang “Carol of the Bells” (based on the Ukrainian

¹⁰ Compare with norms as “collective expectations about proper behavior for a given identity” (Jepperson, Wendt, and Katzenstein 1996, 54).

¹¹ Compare a rational choice perspective per which rationality and functionality are effectively the same. On the *post hoc ergo propter hoc* fallacy behind functional explanations, see Keohane (1984, 81).

⁸ Compare with Huizinga’s (2016 [1949], 11) discussion of the “spoil-sport” or “the player who trespasses against the rules or ignores them.”

⁹ For another case of ritual disruption and failure at the start of the second Trump presidency, see Koschut (2025).

Table 1. Ritual action in international politics.

Attribute Scope	<i>Rationality</i> <i>Intentional design for ritual action</i>	<i>Functionality</i> <i>Post hoc rationalization of ritual action</i>	<i>Performativity</i> <i>Established effects of ritual action</i>
<i>General</i>	Navigating radical uncertainty Enchanting political interactions	Ontological security generation Production of social cohesion	Drawing boundaries of subjectivity and community Producing social magic: giving meaning through affective charge Ordering or disordering international institutions
<i>Intermediate</i>	Mediating ambiguity in concrete interactions	Negotiating and reconciling ambiguous interactions	Maintaining or disrupting status quo Performing intentions
<i>Immediate</i>	Effective performance	Materializing and managing international interactions	Projecting an identity

song “Shchedryk”) in the Latvian forest in December 2022,¹² this mediated ritual of sending season’s greetings on behalf of the North Atlantic Alliance concurrently expressed solidarity with Ukraine at the time of its subjection to large-scale Russian aggression; symbolized, communicated, and enacted NATO’s multinational togetherness in the Alliance’s eastern flank and provided an emotional framing for NATO’s extended deterrence messaging toward Russia. Whether or not such ritual enactment of allied community and solidarity with Ukraine enhanced or eroded the deterrent messaging vis-à-vis Russia remains in the eye of the recipient: singing unanimity, peace, and support to Ukraine by a military alliance could come across as but a mindless soft power appeal for the hard power-gearred aggressor. Like deterrence at large, rituals cannot be verified: their perceived effectiveness depends on whether people believe in them (Kurtz et al. 1988, 72).

The essential element of ritual action in world politics is “what people want to change through ritual” (Lan 2018). In modern IR, ritual action can thus be presumed to be functionally rational, following Karl Mannheim’s distinction; that is, it is “organized with reference to a definite goal,” and adjustable toward in calculating one’s own actions.¹³ Embracing such an understanding resonates with Bell’s preferred treatment of ritualization as a verb rather than a noun (Stephenson 2018a). Her broad understanding of ritual as “the strategic production of expedient schemes that structure an environment” directly informs my take on ritual action in world politics (Bell 2009 [1992], 140). I further concur with Grimes (2013, 193), who finds treating events as more or less ritualized, depending on the qualities that appear in them, more productive than understanding actions as binary (either “ritual” or “not ritual”).

Methodologically, since ritual can only be understood in conjunction with its supposed role or function, ritual action needs to be studied in practice: addressing the core questions of how a particular community ritualizes, and when and why ritualization is deemed to be the effective thing to do. While scripted by convention and tradition regulating practice, ritual action is enacted by real bodies in real places. It thus shares the inclination for an ethnographic approach with close-range participant observation, in-depth immersion, and emic encounters in the field with the study of practices, to be combined with the exploration of the discursive

“liturgy” of the said action in IR. While distinguishing ritual intentions from ritual effects and functions makes sense analytically, demonstrating the mechanics of the performative work of rituals remains methodologically demanding in practice. The analytical process calls for (1) a thick description of the respective interaction ritual chains (Collins 2004), in order to unpeel distinct meanings conveyed by identical physical movements in pertinent cultural contexts; (2) careful tracking of their intended and unintended material and psychological effects in line with their reported responses from the targeted actors and audiences; (3) tracing the historical practices that have given rise to the interaction ritual chains in question; historicizing the respective narratives, concepts, and categories; (4) dissecting the cultural meanings ascribed to particular political enactments, that is, unpacking the framing of certain political rituals and the taken-for-granted assumptions about them; and (5) delineating the political rationalities underpinning ritualization as a genre of action in IR. For example, an actionable analytical framework for the study of deterrence interaction ritual chains needs to accordingly specify who are the actors doing deterrence, what are their distinct roles in the interaction chains of deterrence, what is the situational setting or time-space of the happening of deterrence and the political context of threat formulation, what are the symbolic expressions of reciprocity, the related rules, and the history of pertinent precedence, and what makes the said interaction chains ritual-like in the first place (compare Jönsson and Hall 2005, 50–8).

In sum, ritual action unfolds in the symbolic ground where there is a stake, but we cannot calculate or measure its cost but in rational terms, yet convincing threats and promises have to be conveyed for the action to make intersubjectively sense and matter politically. This opens new research vistas to rationality and creativity of action (Joas 1996), ontological security management at the interstate, and order-making at the international level. Unless we understand ritual action in world politics, we are unable to grasp why actors put their faith in and seek to rationalize practices that remain rationally immeasurable or plainly irrational, and effectively generative of the very radical uncertainty they seek to mitigate (nuclear deterrence being the case in point). Bringing ritualization in the analytical focus of IR advances the understanding of the processes of mitigating radical uncertainty, mediating ambiguity about others’ intentions, and generating credibility about one’s own in international politics.

¹²<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jBaOO5CngMk>

¹³“Functional” rationality is thus distinguished from “substantive” rationality, which designates certain ends as superior to or worse than alternative ends (Tilman 2004, 164–5).

A Guide to Articles

This special forum grew out of the inaugural ERC RITUAL DETERRENCE workshop at the University of Copenhagen in October 2023 and the follow-on workshop on the island of Cres in the framework of the CEEISA-ISA Joint International Conference at the University of Rijeka in June 2024. The original momentum for this collective venture can be traced back to the 2018 European Workshops in International Studies (EWIS) at the University of Groningen, where Tanja Aalberts and Anna Leander convened a group of scholars studying rituals in world politics. Various constellations of contributing scholars have convened for thematic panels at the annual International Studies Association (ISA), European International Studies Association (EISA), and British International Studies Association (BISA) conferences in the build-up to this special forum ever since.

The articles in this special forum make three main contributions. First, they show how ritual and ritualization structure some of the core practices of IR, and our knowledge-production of them. Such a focus expands the ontology of world politics and zooms in on an underappreciated dynamic in IR. The focus on ritual opens a novel analytical register in the study of world politics, privileging the situational, the contextual, the ceremonial, the affective, the performative, the bodily, and the rhythmic. Second, the analytical concentration on rituals in global politics allows us to ask new research questions and revisit some of the well-settled concepts and their operational logics in the practice and theory of world politics. Acknowledging the ritual features and dynamics in deterrence implies a rethinking of signaling in the study of this central international security practice. In the realm of diplomatic encounters, the relation of face-to-face and small-group interaction rituals to international spectacles, such as diplomatic summits, commemoration ceremonies, and military parades calls for a ritual-attentive scrutiny. The examination of ritualized knowledge production patterns on the international enables to highlight dubious epistemic habits in the study of world politics in turn. Third, through the contributors' engagement with ongoing debates in ontological security studies, international practices, emotions, affect, and performativity in international politics, the forum speaks to an array of contemporary IR debates from a ritual entry point.

Jorg Kustermans makes a conceptual contribution to this special forum. He engages critically with the argument that ritual is a "useful resource" for political actors and the instrumental conception of ritual action that informs this argument. Drawing from the rich history of ritual theory, he seeks to unsettle the self-evidence of instrumental accounts of ritual action and create an opening for non-instrumental interpretations of ritual activity. Ritual actors do not have to be theorized as "agents" who manipulate ritual practices as a resource in pursuit of their political ambitions, but can also be conceived as "protagonists" who engage in ritual action instinctively, in response to weighty situations and by way of deep-rooted models. Crucially, in this process, ritual actors become archetypal characters and the substantial situations they find themselves confronted with achieve universal significance, without necessarily having much further consequence. Kustermans illustrates the interpretive merit of instrumental and non-instrumental approaches to ritual action in a double reading of Willy Brandt's 1970 genuflection in Warsaw.

The next set of contributions zoom in on the rituals of deterrence and defense in IR across distinct multilateral sites and key global actors. Kjøløv Egeland's article offers an inves-

tigation into the origins and functions of "central rites" in nuclear policy practice. Whereas nuclear statecraft is often seen as a field of policy characterized by restraint and streamlined economic rationality, Egeland demonstrates how the practices that constitute it are helped along symbolic imagery and ritualistic behavior. Arguing that rituals can help foster conformity, cohesion, and cooperation in contexts where credibility is lacking and preferences are divided, Egeland demonstrates how rituals are deployed to overcome key problems in nuclear statecraft, including the challenge of encouraging obedience throughout the nuclear chain of command, the imperative of securing international buy-in for nuclear policies, and the difficulties associated with facilitating structured communication between adversarial states. Empirically, the discussion draws on Russian nuclear deterrence practice, NATO's Nuclear Planning Group, and multilateral nuclear disarmament diplomacy at the United Nations (UN).

Cameron Hunter's contribution delves into the ways China's People's Liberation Army Rocket Force (PLARF) uses ritual-like practices to convey specific political messages around Party control of nuclear weapons and soldiers' willingness to die for the state. Building on Catherine Bell's take on ritualization and Randall Collins's framework of interaction ritual chains, Hunter maintains that ritualization turns solemn policy statements into something Chinese elites can feel reassured by while seeking to deter hostile governments. Official doctrine calls for the meticulously choreographed display of weapons and troops, highlighting their excellent technical abilities, loyalty to the Party, and soldiers' willingness to sacrifice themselves. Rituals produce the shared emotional energy required to activate troops. Meanwhile, with the audiovisual circulation of these ceremonies and exercises, PLARF leaders create symbols and meanings that overspill the immediate scene of the concrete ritual, creating new encounters with the targeted domestic and international audiences. With ritualizations of solidarity, symbolic repair, and sacrifice, the PLARF addresses multiple goals and audiences.

Mariia Vladymyrova investigates Russian naval exercises in the Baltic Sea in recent years as a ritual-like "show of force." Her contribution conceptualizes strategic posturing through the analysis of the symbolic significance of military exercises, emphasizing their performative nature, the significance of the spaces they encompass, and their function in communicating deterrent signals to diverse audiences. Framed as visually charged, patterned, and symbolic performances, military exercises richly contribute to our comprehension of ritual action in global politics. Vladymyrova shows how Russia's ritualization of its strategic posturing in the Baltic Sea not only enhances its readiness and sea control, but also symbolically asserts Russian presence and historical claims in the region.

Amir Lupovici's article investigates the war in Ukraine through the combined analytical lenses of deterrence, ontological security, and ritual scholarship. He maintains that relying on the delivery of arms to Ukraine as part of the alliance's deterrence by denial strategy of Russia's war aims has provided opportunities to validate NATO's narratives and routines, and thus also ways to address the alliance's ontological security needs. Rituals around NATO summits and military training have helped to constitute the alliance's extended deterrence messaging, while providing crucial ontological security benefits to the allies.

The four consecutive contributions take the conversation to the realms of foreign policymaking and diplomacy, tapping into wartime as a ritual modality of conducting foreign relations, peacekeeping practices as ritually saturated

sites, the ritualized review process of the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT) in the maintenance of the global nuclear order, and the problem of ritual efficacy on the example of diplomatic rituals.

Andrew R. Hom offers a ritualized wartiming framework drawing on Russia's "special military operation" in Ukraine. Analyzing elite incantations and the annual Victory Day Parade against the backdrop of the venerated liturgy of national triumph, he shows how Putin's regime inaugurated a new form of wartime to authorize and consistently legitimize Russia's war against Ukraine. Hom highlights the dangerous potential of such ritualized wartiming to evolve toward a de facto "normal" time of politics.

Drawing on in-depth original interviews, Vanessa Newby and Chiara Ruffa investigate the Tripartite Meetings hosted by the United Nations Interim Force in Lebanon (UNIFIL) to illuminate the ritual intricacies in peace and conflict settings. Analyzing the micro-processes of military diplomacy involved in the Tripartites, the authors show how these encounters ritualized the containment of mutual blame, resentment and victimhood, instead of resolving tensions or advancing political rapprochement. On the one hand, the ritualized nature of the interactions within the Tripartites between the representatives of the Lebanese Armed Forces and the Israel Defense Forces ensured micro-level predictability and helped to keep security incidents in check. On the other, the meetings failed to serve as a precursor for conflict resolution and a broader peace.

Juha A. Vuori applies the lens of ritual action to examine the role of the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT) review process in maintaining the global nuclear order. His article showcases the interwovenness of nuclear diplomacy with the maintenance of identities, social orders, and emotion management. Whereas the ritual of the NPT review process maintains a hierarchical nuclear deterrence order and the legitimacy of nuclear deterrence as institutionalized strategic practice, the Humanitarian Initiative within the review process and the subsequent Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons (TPNW) have come to disrupt it, undermining the legitimacy of nuclear weapons possession and, by extension, nuclear deterrence.

Thierry Balzacq's contribution closes the special forum's subsection on ritual action in diplomacy. Taking a deep dive in the debates on ritual efficacy, Balzacq critically engages with the notions of expressive, instrumental, doctrinal, operational, asserted and actual efficacy. He develops a context-specific account as an alternative to attempts to create a universal theory of efficacy. Diplomatic order and ritual "are inextricably entangled," and the efficacy of diplomatic ritual boils down to its informative capacity, argues Balzacq.

The final section of the special forum tackles the knowledge production rituals in the study of IR. Thomas Fraise zeroes in on the figure of the "nuclear expert," which emerged in the context of the radically new challenges of nuclear weapons, claiming authority over knowledge production in the field of nuclear strategy. The mix of secrecy and ritualistic claims of this esoteric craft transformed figures such as Bernard Brodie, Thomas Schelling, or Daniel Ellsberg into the "magicians" of nuclear strategy, whose epistemic authority was grounded in the ability to claim crucial knowledge about uncertain and dangerous endeavors, as Fraise maintains.

Christian Bueger's article offers an ethnographically embedded reflection on multinational military gatherings as locations of ritualized practices in state interaction. Building on ethnographic observations obtained in attending many naval gatherings across the world, Bueger shows how these

meetings have a common structure and are driven by symbolic contents and ritualized actions, such as gift exchanges, the celebration of food and culture, and recurrent mantras. The ritual elements of naval symposiums facilitate transnational maritime security communities by building the trust and shared understanding for effective maritime security cooperation.

The forum concludes with a closing reflection by Dorothy Noyes on its collective contributions in the context of IR and ritual scholarship.

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